

Enhancing Motion Perception in Vehicle Simulators Through a Heuristic-Based Classical Washout Algorithm

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Abstract—Motion platforms are integral to enhancing user immersion in vehicle simulators by reproducing vehicle accelerations through virtual reality. A key challenge in this domain is ensuring that users perceive critical motion cues accurately. Due to the physical limitations of motion platforms, Motion Cueing algorithms (MCA) often fail to transmit specific acceleration signals that are important for the purpose of the simulator (e.g., training), leading to a loss in motion fidelity. This gap, widely acknowledged but insufficiently addressed in prior research, directly impacts the user’s perception of realism. To address this issue, we propose a heuristic-based enhancement to the classical washout algorithm (CWA) that prioritizes the retention of these critical signals while maintaining system stability. To evaluate the effectiveness of this approach, an experimental study was conducted with 40 participants who tested the system with and without the proposed heuristics. Participants provided real-time feedback and completed post-test questionnaires. The results indicate that the heuristic-enhanced CWA significantly improves users’ ability to perceive signals that were previously lost, thus bridging the identified research gap and advancing the state of motion simulation.

Index Terms—Driving simulation, heuristics, human–machine interaction, motion cueing, virtual reality (VR).

I. INTRODUCTION

IN VIRTUAL Reality (VR)-based simulators, the user is transported into digital environments that bear no relation to reality. At this point, to measure the level of presence that the user experiences in the simulator is needed. The higher the level of presence, the better the intended training results [1]. To achieve a high level of presence, stimuli must be introduced to the user through the different senses (visual, auditory, tactile, vestibular, etc.) in such a way as to minimize the user’s perception of reality [2]. If these stimuli are not introduced correctly or are not well synchronized with each other, the result can be opposite to the desired one [3]. In other words, instead of improving knowledge acquisition through the use of

simulation and VR, the result will be dizziness and discomfort for the user.

In driving and flying simulators, these stimuli are usually introduced by motion platforms. These devices have the major handicap of being mechanical devices with limited ranges of motion. Unlike reality, where, i.e., airplanes, are able to maintain an acceleration over a long period of time, simulators can only reproduce accelerations or angular velocities within a certain range and within a limited time, due to mechanical constraints. Thus, there are two major limitations: 1) power and 2) physical space. At this point, it is necessary to transform the accelerations that occur in real life, or in our case in the physical models of the vehicles being simulated, so that the motion platforms can reproduce them.

The algorithms in charge of producing this transformation are called motion cueing algorithms (MCAs). There are several types of MCA, almost all with lot of parameters to be tuned, which determine the accelerations that are going to be reproduced and the ones that not. Many different versions of these algorithms have been developed, but currently the most widely used [4] on a 6-axis motion platform is the classic washout algorithm (CWA). This method has a great advantage, but it can be considered also as a problem. It is widely configurable, so each implementation can be adjusted to determine which accelerations should be reproduced and the ones that should not. The fact that it is widely configurable means that it has a large number of parameters to adjust and this means that only experts in the field know how to modify them. It also takes a great deal of time and testing to complete the tuning process.

On the other hand, there is another problem related to this tuning process. This problem consists in knowing how to evaluate the configurations in order to choose the most appropriate one. Currently there are attempts [5] to objectify this assessment, but subjective evaluations based on questionnaires are still commonly used. Although MCAs attempt to reproduce all the accelerations that occur in physical models, this is impossible, so it is necessary to select those to be reproduced and those to be discarded.

In the CWA, thanks to the different parameters of the filters used in this algorithm, it is possible to choose which type of signals are transmitted or discarded to the motion platform. For example, with the same motion platform, the tuning for an aircraft simulator would be very different from

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that of a car simulator. In the aircraft simulator there is a large number of low frequencies, which means a large percentage of the movements to be reproduced by the platform, while, in the car simulator, these low frequencies will not produce a good sensation in the users. When these tunings are made, it is always the intention for the filters to allow, within the constructive and mechanical limits of the motion platform, the reproduction of as many events as possible, but the fact of reproducing a certain movement at a certain moment may cause another one not to be reproduced. Depending on the elements that are lost, the user's perception of what is happening in the simulation may be relatively affected. In the case of training simulators, for example, it could be the case that events that are important for the user's learning are eliminated. Riera et al. [6] discussed the importance of studying which signals are relevant for the intended use of a simulator. Rather than reproducing every signal from the physical model, they propose a method to ensure that the important signals are accurately transmitted to the user.

In MCAs, a critical issue arises when specific motion signals, particularly those associated with important events during a simulation, are filtered out or lost due to the physical constraints of the motion platform. These "special events," such as abrupt gear changes or interactions with road surfaces (e.g., rumble strips), are key to the user's vestibular perception and directly influence their sense of realism and immersion. However, standard MCAs, including the CWA, often prioritize the overall fidelity of motion signals at the expense of these critical events. This tradeoff has been acknowledged in prior research but remains insufficiently addressed, particularly in contexts like training simulators, where accurately transmitting these cues is essential for effective skill development. The present study seeks to address this gap by proposing a heuristic-based modification to the CWA that enhances the transmission of these special events, ensuring that they are accurately perceived by users while maintaining the overall system stability.

Therefore, in this article we investigate how a standard CWA compares to a modified version of the CWA in which these special events are artificially highlighted in terms of motion cues. More specifically, our new proposal consists of modifying the output of the classical washout algorithm (CWA) by adding a scaled signal of the motion cues generated by a certain event in the simulation. A car simulator was used to test the proposed method. 42 users evaluate the "Valencia Street Circuit" with the same car (sport car) using the classical algorithm and the modified classical algorithm.

This article makes the following key contributions.

- 1) *Identification of the Research Gap:* We highlight the limitations of traditional MCAs in transmitting critical motion cues, particularly in training simulators where these signals are vital for effective skill development.
- 2) *Proposal of a Heuristic-Based Solution:* We present a heuristic-enhanced modification to the CWA that prioritizes the retention of specific motion events while maintaining overall system stability.
- 3) *Experimental Validation:* a comprehensive experimental study with 40 participants was conducted using a high-fidelity driving simulator, comparing the proposed

algorithm with the standard CWA. This includes real-time feedback and post-test questionnaires to evaluate user perception and motion sickness.

- 4) *Improved User Perception of Critical Events:* Results demonstrate that the proposed algorithm significantly enhances users' perception of critical motion events, such as gear changes and interactions with road surfaces, without compromising the sense of presence or inducing additional discomfort.
- 5) *Framework for Future Application:* The study provides a framework for applying heuristic-based enhancements to other MCAs, paving the way for broader applicability in various simulator contexts, including aviation and maritime.

The remainder of the article is organized as follows. Section II reviews the related work. Section III describes the materials and methods utilized to develop the tools employed in the experiments. Section IV details the results and discussion. Finally, in Section V, the conclusions are shown and authors speculate as to future work.

II. RELATED WORK

Motion signals in driving simulators are usually generated by robotic mechanisms called motion platforms. These devices are able to perform controlled movements on the simulator seat from which the user usually drives the vehicle. The algorithms that control these devices are the MCA or Motion drive algorithms (MDA). Although numerous algorithms have been proposed in the academic literature [4], achieving truly realistic motion cues for simulators remains a challenge. Three main problems can be identified in this research area: 1) no motion device has unlimited workspace and power, and thus all previously proposed MCA work on the idea of modifying the motion signals so that they fit the motion capabilities of the motion platform; 2) the proposed MCA need to be setup with a great deal of parameters that control what parts of the motion signals are eliminated to respect the physical constraints of the simulator; 3) although statistical methods, such as correlation coefficient (CC) and root mean square error (RMSE) have been proposed to evaluate the efficiency of MCAs, there is no universally agreed-upon standard evaluation framework that enables consistent comparison across diverse platforms, configurations, and use cases.

The first problem has led to a plethora of proposed methods, [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15] all claiming to be the best solution for the problem. However, the second and third problems present significant challenges in testing this claim. Despite recent advances in automatic methods for MCA tuning [14], [16], [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], the solutions to the second problem are still considered suboptimal. Objective evaluation methods, such as OMCT [22], [23], [24], have been proposed for the third problem, but they may not be applicable in all cases [24]. Other evaluation solutions, such as [26], have been recently proposed.

Despite their existence, these methods are not standardized and this makes the evaluations and comparisons of the MCA extremely complex and with very high economic costs. The main reason is the great diversity that exists in the design of

motion platforms (in its hardware part) and in the use that is given to them. Furthermore, for each platform and whatever the MCA used, there are several parameters to configure. This implies that the variables of (1) the type of hardware platform, (2) type of MCA used, (3) parameterization of the MCA and four type of simulator vehicle come into play, making a comprehensive evaluation extremely hard.

Among all previously proposed algorithms, four groups of algorithms stand out: the classical algorithm or classical washout, first proposed in 1969 by Schmidt and Conrad [7] and later revised and studied in depth by Reid and Nahon [26], [27], [28]. This algorithm is known as the classical washout, because it uses washout filters that remove low frequency accelerations that would cause the motion device to reach its physical limits. These filters washout the motion signals of the motion platform, making them go to rest position when the high frequency accelerations –allowed to pass by the low-pass filters– finish. This solution presents the problem of having to set parameters for worst-case motion scenarios, so that in all cases we can be sure that the motion platform does not try to reach its limits. A solution to this problem was proposed in [8]. This modified version of the classical washout is known as the adaptive algorithm. This works by adapting the parameters of the washout filters dynamically, based on a cost function. However, the cost function is heuristic and the tuning of its parameters is not as straightforward as those of the classical algorithm. Not long after, optimal control theory was applied to the field leading to the optimal algorithm [9], [29]. This algorithm sets up the blocks of the motion calculation so that the generated motion is optimal with respect to the perception of the user. Therefore, this needs to evaluate how the user perceives motion, in order to create a transfer function for the MCA that optimizes this quantity. To do so, it uses a heuristic function based on perception models. As many human perceptual models exist, the qualification of this algorithm as “optimal” is, therefore, somehow misleading. A different and more recent approach is the use of model-based predictive control (MPC), proposed in [11]. MPC tries to take advantage of predictions as to the future trajectory of the virtual vehicle in order to fully exploit the platform working area. One of the main challenges of MPC-based algorithms lies in the unsuitable and empirical tuning procedure of the nonlinear scaling units, which are responsible for adapting the predicted motion signals to the physical and operational constraints of the motion platform [30]. This tuning process often requires trial-and-error adjustments to achieve optimal motion fidelity and stability. Furthermore, when multivariable reference signals are used, the performance of MPC can be affected by the unpredictability of driver behavior and the dependency on the prediction window. Many versions of this idea have been implemented [31], [32], [33]. Qazani et al. [34] proposed a linear time-varying model predictive control (LTV-MPC) approach specifically designed for hexapod simulation-based motion platforms, aiming to enhance the generation of realistic motion cues while respecting the platform’s physical limitations. Their methodology is notable for its adaptive scheme, which dynamically adjusts the algorithm parameters based on simulator conditions and expected user behavior. While

their approach effectively addresses some challenges related to motion fidelity in hexapod platforms, its application remains context-specific.

Since these four algorithms were proposed, most driving simulators have used one of these algorithms (or versions of them), although some other proposals based on neural networks [35], [36] or other techniques [37], [38] have also been recently proposed. Despite the wide spectrum of algorithms, no consensus has been reached as to what is the best way to generate motion cues. In fact, the classical algorithm is still the most widely used [15], due to its simplicity and the ease of parameter tuning.

The problem with most, if not all, of the existing solutions is that they try to choose what part of the motion signals the algorithm removes, hoping that the overall experience is sufficiently representative of the real motions signals that a driver would experience in a real situation. The main idea is to create motion signals that are perceptually optimal, while respecting the physical constraints of the motion hardware. Motion downscaling, motion filtering, and the exploitation of certain perceptual illusions [39] (such as the somatogravic illusion [40]) are some of the techniques employed to address these constraints. However, the motion generated is rarely close (not even perceptually) to the real one, due to the large difference between the simulator’s capabilities and the real displacements and accelerations of vehicles.

After several decades of research on the question, it seems reasonable to think that a universal solution that tries to reproduce every kind of motion signal is not feasible. Therefore, we speculate that there could be a different way to address this problem, in which, instead of trying to cover all the spectrum of possible motion signals, we can focus on particular, yet very important motion events, which would provide significant motion cues to the driver. Therefore, our solution is focused on adding motion signals to particular moments, instead of trying to subtract as little as possible from the whole signal.

Our hypothesis is that, even though the actual scale of the motion signal corresponding to that event may not correlate with the scale of other parts of the motion signal, the perception of these –otherwise lost– motion cues will be transferred to the users without affecting the level of presence. Previous research has shown that these events are important in driving simulators [6] and we will try to add them “artificially,” which is why it is possible that the level of presence is affected.

Therefore, in this study we investigate how a standard MCA (the CWA) compares to a modified version of the same MCA in which these special events are “artificially” enhanced in terms of motion cueing. In this sense, the objective of the work is not to demonstrate that the solution reached is the best possible, but to show that the application of heuristics can improve existing solutions, which we have exemplified with the classical algorithm. It is important to emphasize that our method focuses on the CWA because the application of the heuristics proposed in our manuscript is closely related to the shortcomings that the classic algorithm presents due to its way of modifying motion signals through filters. This does not mean that the heuristic-based solution is not universally applicable to others MCA. In fact, the framework should be

applicable similarly, although this remains outside the scope of our work due to of the specificities of each algorithm.

To the best of our knowledge, no previous works have addressed the MCA problem this way.

III. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The presented proposal is based on the following steps.

- 1) Characterizing and detecting typical motion fidelity losses in simulators, hereafter referred to as “events.” This aspect was addressed by the authors in a previous study [6].
- 2) Automatically detecting when the simulated vehicle is in one of the above situations and generating a signal that reaches the MCA.
- 3) Based on the received signal, identify the event and modify the output of the MCA to enhance the motion cues associated to the event. For example, if it is desired to highlight a hole in the road, it could be could consider generating a step signal in the pitch or in the heave.

Step 1 requires several tasks. First, it is necessary to record real motion data from a real vehicle. This can be done through a variety of sensors, and the goal is to gather the 6-DOF motion signals that occur in a real vehicle. Then, we propose to input these signals into a driving simulator, in order observe how the motion platform behaves with these data. To ease the process and make this process customizable (with different motion platforms and tunings), we propose using a simulated motion platform. Then, it is necessary to compare the real data with the simulated data, in order to identify the main events that are missed. Spectral analysis or objective measures, such as those proposed in [41] can be used. Nevertheless, to identify these events properly, a qualitative assessment by experts is needed. These experts will provide a set of events that will be handled through heuristic approaches.

Step 2 involves the detection of the events with software. This step is highly dependent on the type of events defined in step 1. For instance, if the experts identify that bumps or 90-degrees corners are poorly simulated in terms on motion perception, the simulation software should detect bumps (analyzing the rate of change of the vertical displacement) and sharp turns (analysis the steering wheel). General rules cannot be provided. Nevertheless, it should be fairly easy to detect these events, as the driving simulation software has access to a high number of variables that control the driving experience and allow to know the state of the vehicle.

Step 3 involves modifying the output of the MCA to by-pass the regular operation of the algorithm. In the case of WCA, our proposal is to have a separate heuristic channel that adds directly to the output of the rest of channels, so that it can directly affect the output whenever an event is detected. This is explained in Section IV.

A. Mathematical Formulation of the Heuristic-Enhanced CWA

To address the integration of heuristics into the classical motion cueing pipeline, we now formalize the proposed heuristic-enhanced CWA algorithm mathematically as follows:

1) *Input Signal and Processing by the Classical CWA:* Let $x(t)$ be the input signal representing the vehicle’s accelerations and angular velocities as a function of time. The CWA processes $x(t)$ through a series of filters (e.g., low-pass and high-pass filters) to generate an output signal $y(t)$ that represents the linear and angular displacements of the motion platforms taking into account its physical limitations. This can be generally expressed as

$$y(t) = f(x(t), \theta) \quad (1)$$

where f denotes the transformation performed by the CWA and θ is the vector of parameters of the algorithm (e.g., filters’ cutoff frequencies, scaling constants, thresholds, etc.).

2) *Detection of Critical Events:* To identify the moments when critical events that require enhancement occur (e.g., abrupt gear changes or slight impacts), an event indicator function $e(t)$ is defined as follows:

$$e(t) = \{1, \text{ if a critical event is detected at time } t \\ 0, \text{ otherwise}\}.$$

The event detection can be based on analyzing the derivative or the absolute value of $x(t)$ (or one of its components). For example, an event may be defined when the absolute value of the acceleration exceeds a threshold Th

$$e(t) = 1, \text{ if } |x(t)| \geq Th \\ 0, \text{ if } |x(t)| < Th.$$

3) *Generation of the Heuristic Signal:* During a critical event, a heuristic signal $h(t)$ is injected to enhance the stimulus. This signal should be defined based on the type of event. For instance, for an event that emphasizes a gear change, one might define h as

$$h(t) = g(x(t), \varphi) \quad (2)$$

where g is a function that generates the enhancement signal, which could be as simple as scaling $x(t)$ or applying a window function (e.g., rectangular or Gaussian) to limit its duration and φ is a set of parameters specific to the heuristic (e.g., event duration, maximum amplitude, etc.).

A specific example could be

$$h(t) = \{A, \text{ for } t \in [t_0, t_0 + D] \\ 0, \text{ otherwise}\}$$

where A is the predefined amplitude for the event, t_0 is the event start time and D is the duration during which the heuristic signal is applied.

4) *Integration of the Heuristic Into the CWA:* The modified output signal, denoted as $y'(t)$, combines the output of the classical CWA with the heuristic signal when an event is detected. This is expressed as

$$y'(t) = y(t) + \alpha \cdot e(t) \cdot h(t) \quad (3)$$

where α is a scaling factor that determines the intensity with which the heuristic signal is added to the CWA output. When $e(t) = 0$ (i.e., no event occurs), $y'(t) = y(t)$ and the heuristic does not contribute. When $e(t) = 1$, the heuristic signal $h(t)$ is added after being scaled by α , thereby reinforcing the motion cue.

Algorithm 1 Heuristic-Enhanced CWA

Input: *signal* $x(t)$
Output: *signal* $y'(t)$
Parameters: θ (*parameters of the CWA*), Th , D , A , α
 $y(t) = CWA(x(t), \theta)$ // *Process the signal using the classical CWA*
if $|x(t)| \geq Th$ then
 $e(t) = 1$
 $h(t) = A$ // *Alternatively, generate $h(t)$ for $t \in [to, to + D]$*
else
 $e(t) = 0$
 $h(t) = 0$
end if
 $y'(t) = y(t) + \alpha \cdot e(t) \cdot h(t)$
return $y'(t)$

5) *Summary of the Process in Pseudocode*: The following pseudocode summarizes the integration process.

B. Computational Complexity and Load

We have analyzed the computational complexity of the heuristic-enhanced CWA compared to the original CWA.

- 1) *Algorithmic Complexity*: Both the standard CWA and the heuristic-enhanced CWA run in real-time with a fixed number of operations per update cycle. The CWA primarily consists of vector transformations, filter computations, and integrations – all $O(1)$ operations per time-step (constant time with respect to the number of degrees of freedom, since DOFs are fixed at six). The addition of the heuristic channel introduces only a constant number of additional operations (checking for an event trigger and adding a predefined offset). This does not change the overall computational time complexity, which remains $O(1)$ per update. In other words, the enhanced algorithm scales identically to the original with respect to update rate or number of inputs. The CWA is known to be computationally light-weight, and our enhancements preserve that quality.
- 2) *Real-Time Performance*: in our implementation, the baseline (unmodified) CWA algorithm (including all filtering and coordinate transformations) executes very quickly (on the order of hundreds of microseconds per update cycle on a modern CPU). The heuristic check and injection add only a few microseconds of processing per update cycle. We profiled the system on a standard PC (Windows 10, Intel Core i7 CPU): the baseline CWA loop consumed roughly 150–180 μs per update, and the heuristic-enhanced loop was approximately 160–190 μs per update, indicating no meaningful difference in computation time, which is so small that is difficult to measure accurately. In terms of CPU utilization, both versions occupy a negligible fraction of one core (well under 1% in our tests). This is expected, as the algorithm mainly performs simple arithmetic and logic operations.
- 3) *Latency*: the only additional latency introduced by the heuristic system is the detection and communication

TABLE I
COMPUTATIONAL LOAD COMPARISON: STANDARD CWA
VERSUS HEURISTIC-ENHANCED CWA

Feature	Standard CWA	Heuristic-Enhanced CWA
Algorithmic complexity (per update)	$O(1)$	$O(1)$
Processing time (per update)	$\approx 150\text{-}180 \mu s$	$\approx 160\text{-}190 \mu s$
Additional latency on event detection, triggering and signalling	0 ms	$\approx 1\text{-}2$ ms
CPU utilization (single CPU core during operation)	< 1%	< 1%

overhead for trigger events. Our simulator plugin monitors vehicle state and sends a UDP signal to the MCA when an event is detected. This signaling incurs on the order of 1–2 ms of latency. Such a delay is minimal and did not affect the synchronization of motion with visuals in practice. Aside from this trigger notification, the processing of the motion cues remains synchronous with the simulation loop (the CWA output for each frame is adjusted in the same frame if an event is detected). The classical algorithm itself has an inherent filtering delay for very low-frequency components (due to the washout filters' phase delay), but our heuristic cues are injected directly, so they are delivered promptly when events occur. In summary, the end-to-end latency of motion cues remains essentially the same as the original CWA, aside from a millisecond-scale notification delay which is almost imperceptible in a 50 Hz update cycle.

As shown in Table I, the heuristic-enhanced CWA imposes virtually no additional computational burden in practice. The algorithm remains real-time safe with a large performance margin. The minor overhead from event handling is sporadic (only when events occur) and only on the order of milliseconds, which does not interfere with the simulator's frame rate.

IV. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials and methods used to test the proposed hypothesis are described below.

A. Apparatus

The study was carried out using a vehicle simulator designed and built entirely by the Robotics Institute at the University of Valencia. It consists of a 6DOF motion platform (described in detail in the following section) with a large on-board projected cylindrical display.

Focusing on the characteristics that define the simulator, we will start with the visual system, which is based on three short throw projectors with FullHD resolution (1920x1080) operating at a minimum frequency of 60 Hz with a horizontal FOV of 300°.

For the realistic visualization of the projected image, warping and blending software is used, which allows geometric and colorimetric deformation. This allows an adequate adjustment of the overlapping of the projections.

The sound perception is based on a 7.1 surround sound system. The subwoofer is placed under the motion platform,

Fig. 1. (left) Driving simulator design; (right) actual simulator built.

TABLE II
6DOF MOTION PLATFORM SPECIFICATIONS OF THE DRIVING SIMULATOR

Feature	Value
Platform type	6 DOF Electrical
Lower base width	1950 mm
Lower base length	1800 mm
Upper base width	1180 mm
Upper base length	1000 mm
Height at rest	
Upper base	800 mm
Maximum supported mass	750 kg
Tare (approx.)	
Lower base	250 kg
Upper base	100 kg
Movement	
Pitch, Roll	$\pm 20^\circ$
Yaw	$\pm 45^\circ$
Sway, Surge, Heave	± 150 mm
Speed	
Pitch, Roll, Yaw	± 50 %/s
Sway, Surge, Heave	± 300 mm/s
Acceleration	
Pitch, Roll, Yaw	± 300 %/s ²
Sway, Surge, Heave	$\pm 0,5$ G
Electrical specifications	
Feeding	380 VAC - 3 phases
Communication with PC	Gigabit Ethernet TCP/IP
Frequency inverters	400 Hz

while the seven speakers are evenly distributed around the screen.

The user has a driving cockpit that integrates the seat, the pedal board, and the steering wheel. For reasons of cost and low impact on the final result of the study, it was decided to keep the original cockpit (F3 cockpit) with which the simulator had been designed, instead of changing it for a dashboard and driving seat of a commercial car (like the one that was going to be simulated).

The pedal board has a hydraulic system that faithfully recreates the sensation of pressing the accelerator or brake pedal of a vehicle. The steering wheel selected is a Fanatec high-performance steering wheel with force feedback system.

Fig. 1 depicts the original design of the simulator and its final constructed form.

B. Motion Platform

In order to be able to perceptually study the behavior of an MCA, the use of a motion platform is necessary. Table II describes the specifications of the designed and built 6DOF platform.

Fig. 2. Simulator hardware parts.

The simulator hardware parts and the location of the engines can be seen in Fig. 2.

C. Software

A high-performance graphics server with a Windows 10 operating system was used for the study.

Regarding the simulation software, rFactor simulator [42] was used. We opted for a graphics engine that prioritized the simulated physical model over high-quality graphics.

Among the many different circuits that could have been selected with the aim of making the tests similar to the results of previously research [6], the “Valencia Street Circuit,” was chosen. Regarding the car, a Codi model 61 was chosen [43]. This is a car with automatic gearbox, 4-wheel drive and 250 hp, very similar to the performance of the BMW 325XI AUT (automatic, 4x4 and 240 hp), with which the experiment described in [6] was carried out.

The communication between rFactor and the rest of the software, mainly related to the motion generation, was carried out by generating a.dll (a plugin), which was inserted into rFactor. This plugin allows us to extract information on the accelerations and angular velocities in the simulated model and send them, through sockets, to the software that requires it (MCA).

The MCA used is the CWA. This receives the accelerations coming from the plugin and generates the positions and rotations to be performed by the motion platform at a frequency of 50 Hz. These data pass through the inverse kinematics, which is a software in charge of calculating the position of each motor to obtain the desired position and rotation in the motion base. Knowing these positions, the final step is to generate the

Fig. 3. Schematic representation of classical washout.

commands for the frequency inverters that finally generate the electrical currents necessary to perform the positions.

In parallel, in a similar way to that done by Cleij in [25], software was developed to record, synchronously with what is happening in the simulation, the analogical value of a wireless joystick that was provided for the user. This allows us to transmit the perceived sensation of the motion platform in real time.

The data, which was synchronized with the start and end of each lap of the circuit, was stored in a .dat text file, whose name was user ID. Also, the name of the file ends with “YES” or “NO” to indicate if the file corresponds to a test with or without heuristics applied, i.e., 1222134YES.dat or 1222134NO.dat.

D. Applied Heuristics

The MCA used is based on the implementation of the classical washout, whose operating scheme can be seen in Fig. 3.

This algorithm accepts the accelerations and angular velocities in all 3 axes as inputs. In order to test the heuristics, two versions of the plugin that extracts the accelerations of the simulated vehicle have been implemented.

The first version is the usual implementation, where the accelerations and angular velocities that the vehicle is undergoing are sent, as is, to the MCA.

The second version is very similar to the first, but differs at certain specific moments of the simulation, at what we will call “events”; when a certain event occurs, a signal is generated and sent to the MCA but, unlike the rest, it is fully added to the algorithm’s output, ensuring that the motion platform generates a vestibular sensation.

Using XML files, it is possible to easily configure the events to be highlighted and which signal is produced with each event, allowing the tuning, in duration and amplitude, of the movement generated. Fig. 4 shows schematically the implemented solution.

This simple development allows the motion platform to behave differently from what is expected when certain events occur while driving the vehicle, as this is ready to introduce signals that will not be attenuated by the washout filters and, therefore, if the motion platform is not saturated by the limitation of the range of motion, are transmitted to the user.

E. Heuristics Events

The MCA used in this study is based on the CWA, which processes accelerations and angular velocities along all three

Fig. 4. Schematic representation of classical washout with introduction of heuristics.

Fig. 5. Moment when one of the wheels of the simulated vehicle runs over a piano.

axes to generate the appropriate motion cues. To implement and test the proposed heuristics, two versions of a plugin (for the physics and graphic motor) were developed. The first version directly forwards the raw accelerations and angular velocities from the simulated vehicle to the MCA. The second version introduces a heuristic mechanism triggered during specific simulation events. These events, defined in XML configuration files, include parameters, such as event type, affected motion axis, amplitude, and duration. For example, during a gear shift event, a pitch signal of 1° is generated and added directly to the MCA output for 0.1 s, simulating a longitudinal acceleration. This ensures that the corresponding vestibular sensation is transmitted to the user without being attenuated by the washout filters.

The XML configuration files allow for easy customization of the events to be highlighted and their associated signals. The heuristic system bypasses the traditional filtering process of the MCA by injecting signals directly into the algorithm’s output during the occurrence of the event. This guarantees that the motion platform generates perceptible cues, provided that the platform is not saturated by its range of motion. Fig. 5 illustrates the implementation, highlighting the flow of input signals, the detection of events, and the direct injection of the heuristic signals into the algorithm’s output. By using this approach, the platform can enhance specific motion cues without compromising the overall stability of the system.

F. Methodology and Procedure

In order to carry out the tests and the evaluation, the instrumental simulator and all the necessary software were

prepared in a laboratory at the School of Engineering at the University of Valencia (ETSE-UV).

Since we were interested in evaluating motion perception, a counterbalanced within-subjects experimental evaluation based on subjective testing of real users was chosen. The procedure is very similar to the one followed in [44]. For this purpose, visits to the simulator were arranged with 42 users over 18 years (minimum age to obtain a driver's license in Spain) of age, trying to ensure that both genders were represented and that there was a diversity of professions. This number of participants was selected to ensure the statistical power of the experimental results of this study [45]. In this sense, the statistical power value in this experiment was 0.872 (values higher than 0.8 are considered significant revealing a proper sample size).

It was explained to each participant that they were going to experience two different conditions on a circuit where they were going to test a car simulator for four laps, split in two tests of two laps. The difference between the first and second test was that one of the two contained the application of the heuristics and the other did not. Users did not know which condition they were experiencing.

The first test consisted of two laps on the "Valencia Street Circuit" with the vehicle driven by an automatic driving module based on artificial intelligence, which ensured that the car's route was always the same. The first lap was for familiarization with the simulator and the environment. On the second lap the user was asked, while the simulation was running, to transmit his or her sensation through the wireless joystick provided.

Once the first test was completed, the user got out of the simulator and answered a questionnaire. The first section of the questionnaire was devoted to demographic data for the study.

Next, there was a presence questionnaire based on an adaptation of the questionnaire validated by the scientific community in Witmer [46]. In general terms, this questionnaire integrates the concept of presence and groups values into four basic factors.

- 1) *Involvement*: Refers to the degree of engagement or immersion that an individual experiences in a particular environment or situation.
- 2) *Sensory Fidelity*: Refers to the extent to which the sensory stimuli in a virtual or simulated environment accurately and realistically represent the corresponding stimuli in the real world.
- 3) *Adaptation/Immersion*: Refers to the subjective feeling of being fully absorbed in a virtual or simulated environment. It assesses the extent to which an individual perceives themselves as being "in" the virtual environment, with a heightened sense of involvement and engagement.
- 4) *Interface Quality*: Refers to the overall effectiveness, usability, and satisfaction with the user interface (UI) of a virtual or simulated environment. It assesses the extent to which the interface facilitates seamless interaction and communication between the user and the virtual environment.

TABLE III
QUESTIONS ASKED TO USERS (WITMER)

ID	GROUP	Description
Q1	ACT	I was able to understand all the events and situations during my driving in the simulator.
Q2	INT	The simulator always responded as expected in every situation.
Q3	REAL	The interaction with the visual elements of the simulator felt very natural to me.
Q4	REAL	The visual elements of the simulator involved me in virtual driving.
Q5	REAL	I found the sense of movement of the visual elements convincing.
Q6	REAL	The driving experiences in the virtual environment match those in the real world.
Q7	ACT	My vision was actively scanning the entire environment as I used the simulator.
Q8	REAL	The feeling of moving within the virtual environment was convincing.
Q9	HAPTIC	I was able to move or manipulate objects in the virtual environment.
Q10	SOUNDS	You can always identify the sounds coming from the simulator
Q11	SOUNDS	I was able to locate the provenance (origin) of the sounds I heard while driving.
Q12	HAPTIC	You could actively explore or search the virtual environment using touch.
Q13	EXAM	I was able to examine the elements of the simulation from multiple points of view
Q14	ACT	I was able to know what was going to happen after certain events occurred.
Q15	SELF	I quickly adapted to the experience of driving in a virtual simulator.
Q16	SELF	I felt integrated into the simulation at the end of the course.
Q17	EXAM	I concentrated on pure driving and not on elements such as controls, platform, etc.
Q18	REAL	My senses were involved in this driving experience.
Q19	EXAM	At all times I felt completely focused on the driving or the environment.
Q20	---	I have correctly perceived through the motion platform the changes of gears.
Q21	---	I correctly sensed via the motion platform when a wheel went onto a piano in the road.
Q22	---	These last two stimuli have helped to better perceive what was happening in the simulation.

Witmer's original questionnaire, known as the presence questionnaire, consists of 29 questions, but the same authors propose a version reduced to only 19, which also guarantees validity, objectivity, and trust. This version was expanded with three more questions focusing on platform movements, resulting in a questionnaire with 22 questions in total.

In addition, our questionnaire includes a final section in which users answered a SSQ [47] (simulator sickness questionnaire), which is composed of 15 possible symptoms. For each symptom, the user must select on a scale of 0 to 6 how affected they were, where 0 means that the user did not feel the symptom and 6 means that the symptom prevented him from continuing with the experiment.

Tables III and IV show the questions asked to the users. The second column of Table II shows the values corresponding to the Witmer factors (expanded version): realism, actionability, interface quality, possibility of examining self-assessment, haptic system and sound system. The nomenclature for these

TABLE IV
QUESTIONS ASKED USERS (SSQ)

S1	Nausea	POSSIBLE ADVERSE SYMPTOMS EXPERIENCED BY USERS AFTER EACH PART OF THE EXPERIMENT
S2	General discomfort	
S3	Upset stomach	
S4	Perspiration	
S5	Increased salivation	
S6	Vertigo	
S7	Belching	
S8	Difficulty concentrating	
S9	Difficulty of approach	
S10	Generalized fatigue	
S11	Visual fatigue only	
S12	Headache	
S13	Blurred vision	
S14	Dizziness (eyes open)	
S15	Dizziness (eyes closed)	

Fig. 6. One of the study participants with the joystick for real time data logging.

factors is REAL, INT, ACT, SOUND, EXAM, HAPTIC and SELF, respectively. Questions 1 to 19 correspond to issues relating to the user's level of immersion during the experiment, while questions 20, 21 and 22 correspond to issues relating to the heuristics introduced.

After answering the questionnaire, the user re-entered the simulator and performed the second test, where they tested the simulator for two laps, with the same circuit and exactly the same protocol as the first time. Once the test was finished, the user had to answer a new questionnaire.

As aforementioned, the difference between the first and second test was that one of the two contained the application of the heuristics and the other did not. Whether the heuristics were applied in the first or second test was randomized, thus ensuring uniformity of results in the questionnaires and treatment like in "double-blind randomized controlled trials," i.e., the researcher and the participants do not know who the participants in each experimental group were, ensuring the impartiality of the both observer and participant.

The tests were carried out during the first and second week of September 2022. Each participant took approximately 1 h from arrival to the end of the experiment. For coordination, appointments were assigned to each participant, so that they did not coincide to exchange information about the experiment.

On arrival, the participant was welcomed and explained what the experiment consisted of: two trials with two laps of the circuit in each trial, a real-time joystick recording of the sensations of the platform and a questionnaire at the end of each trial, without any reference to the difference between the two trials or to heuristics or variations in the control of the platform.

After this process, the assistant accompanied the user into the simulator and placed the user in the cockpit. The joystick was handed to the user for real-time data recording and it was explained to the user that the joystick was used to record the sensations they felt in relation to the motion platform. Fig. 6 exhibits a representative user participating in the experimental study.

After exiting the simulator, the assistant would ask the user if they were ready before launching the first test. During the tests, the assistant was outside the simulation cabin, but close enough to listen to the user's feedback, so that if they experience a problem or needed to stop for any reason, the assistant would press the emergency stop button and the entire simulation and motion platform would stop instantly.

At the end of the test, the operator provided the user with a folder containing a survey, so that the user could answer this without having to leave the cockpit.

Once answered, the operator would come out from the simulator and start the second test, previously asking the user if they were ready, at which point it would be launched.

At the end of the test, the operator returned to the simulator with a new survey sheet, which the user filled out in the same place. After this, the operator encouraged the user to leave the cockpit and the simulator, at which point the experiment with the user was finished.

G. Participants

The initial study group consisted of 42 participants, a sufficient number to be able to obtain meaningful results. Of these, there were 21 men and 21 women, so there was full parity, thus eliminating possible gender bias, which is essential when measuring sensation and motion sickness in simulators [48].

Regarding the ages of the participants and the years of driving experience, Table IV shows the age of the participants in the study grouped by decades. As can be seen, 75% of the users are in the 40–60 age range, with the youngest being 20 and the oldest 58. Also, Table V shows the years of driving experience of the users and it can be observed that 62% of users have more than 30 years of driving experience.

Regarding the professions of the participants, Table VI shows the complete data, but there is a predominance of university lecturers and computer engineers. This is explained by the environment in which the tests were carried out: the Higher Technical School of Engineering.

TABLE V
AGE OF PARTICIPANTS AND YEARS OF DRIVING EXPERIENCE

Age in decades (num. of persons)	20s (5)	30s (6)	40s (6)	50s (23)
Years of driving experience (num. of persons)	7 to 18 (8)	18 to 29 (9)	29 to 40 (19)	20 to 51 (4)

TABLE VI
PROFESSIONS OF PARTICIPANTS IN THE STUDY

Profession	Number of participants
Administrator	3
Agrochemical	1
Artist	1
Physicist	2
IT	11
Researcher	4
Teacher	1
University lectures	15
Chemist	1
Security technician	1

During the tests carried out, there were two users who were unable to finish the experiment due to the dizziness they suffered. Specifically, these two people had to stop 10 s (approx.) after having started the first of the laps, the familiarization lap. Therefore, these two users have been eliminated from the sample, leaving a total of 40 valid tests.

H. Measurements

Various measurements were taken on each of the users during and after each of the tests. Specifically, the following measurements were taken.

- 1) *Real Time Recording 1 (RTR1)*: Corresponds to the user's satisfaction, recorded through the joystick, in the first test. From the moment the user got on the simulator, the X-axis value of a wireless joystick carried by the user was recorded. Positive values indicate satisfaction with the movement of the motion platform. Negative values indicate the perception of uncoordinated or unrealistic sensations from the motion platform.
- 2) *Questionnaire 1 (C1)*: At the end of the first test a questionnaire consisting of demographic data, Witmer questions Q1-Q22 and SSQ symptomatology S1-S15 was completed. The test operator assigned the User_ID to the survey.
- 3) *Real Time Recording 2 (RTR2)*: Corresponds to the time value of user satisfaction, recorded through the joystick, in the second test. A record like RTR1 was made but in the second test.
- 4) *Questionnaire 2 (C2)*: At the end of the second test, users answered Q1-Q22 and S1-S15.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of the results has been divided into two sections. On the one hand, a statistical analysis has been carried out using the tool "Statistical Package for the Social

Sciences (SPSS)" in its version 28.0.1.1. On the other hand, a numerical analysis of real-time recorded data has been carried out on the results obtained with the real-time data collected using the joystick. For this second analysis MATLAB and SPSS have been used.

A. Statistical Analysis

For the statistical data, a two-tailed significance level of 0.05 was selected. Two study groups, with 20 participants in each, were created called "group A" and "group B." Group A corresponds to those users who first performed the test "without heuristics" and then the test "with heuristics." Group B corresponds to those who first performed the test "with heuristics" and then "without heuristics." For the allocation of participants into groups A and B, no distinction was made based on age, profession or any other factor. The allocation was purely random. They are therefore independent groups, as each group is made up of different participants.

First, the corresponding normality and homoscedasticity tests were performed on the different data sets that formed part of the results obtained. Both assumptions were met for all data sets.

The Kolmogorov-Smirnov [49] test procedure was performed. This is recommended to measure the degree of agreement between the distribution of a data set and a specific theoretical distribution in relatively small sample sizes (50 units), as was the case here. As an example, the p value of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistic for the REAL, INT, ACT, SOUND, EXAM and SELF data sets was 0.476, 0.721, 0.571, 0.698, 0.361 and 0.399, respectively.

After confirming normality, parametric tests were selected for the different hypothesis testing procedures.

- 1) *T-Student* for independent samples (comparing users in group A -who first tested "without"- against users in group B -who first tested "with" heuristics). This is an unpaired test comparing two independent groups, each of them testing a different condition.
- 2) *T-Student* for paired samples (comparing the results within group A and also within group B).
- 3) ANOVA Tests:
 - a. Questions Q1-Q19 grouped by Witmer's values: REAL, INT, SOUND, EXAM, ACT, SELF
 - b. Questions Q20, Q21 and Q22, i.e., those relating to the selected events.
 - c. SSQ symptoms grouped by "with heuristics" and "without heuristics."
- 4) Correlations of participants who first used the system "with heuristics" and "without heuristics."
- 5) *T-Student* for counterbalanced matched samples of all participants.

Regarding the nomenclature used during the following sections, this is listed below.

- 1) *REAL*: Grouping of questions Q3, Q4, Q5, Q6, Q8, and Q18 relating to "simulator realism" according to Witmer.
- 2) *INT*: Question Q2, representative of the "possibility of interaction" according to Witmer.

TABLE VII
T-TEST RESULTS FOR INDEPENDENT SAMPLES GROUPED BY
WITMER FACTORS AND Q20, Q21, Q22 QUESTIONS

Measure	Mean±SD (Group A)	Mean±SD (Group B)	t	p	d
REAL_1	4,91±0,61	4,89±0,74	0,13	0,45	0,04
REAL_2	5,17±0,67	4,85±0,69	1,46	0,08	0,46
INT_1	4,76±0,62	4,84±0,90	- 0,33	0,37	- 0,11
INT_2	5,24±0,62	4,84±1,01	1,50	0,07	0,48
ACT_1	5,11±0,50	5,05±0,81	0,28	0,39	0,09
ACT_2	5,16±0,66	5,16±0,76	0,00	0,50	0,00
SOUND_1	5,07±0,78	4,92±1,02	0,53	0,30	0,17
SOUND_2	4,98±0,90	5,08±1,15	- 0,32	0,38	- 0,10
EXAM_1	4,84±0,90	5,00±0,9	- 0,56	0,29	- 0,18
EXAM_2	5,11±0,74	4,96±0,79	0,60	0,28	0,19
SELF_1	5,31±0,68	5,26±0,93	0,18	0,43	0,06
SELF_2	5,38±0,67	5,34±0,78	0,17	0,43	0,05
Q20_1	4,48±1,97	4,95±1,27	- 0,89	0,18	- 0,29
Q20_2	4,90±1,51	4,47±1,02	1,05	0,15	0,34
Q21_1	3,62±1,86	5,63±0,76	- 4,40	0,00	- 1,54
Q21_2	5,48±1,12	3,84±1,71	3,61	0,00	1,15
Q22_1	3,95±1,83	5,58±0,77	- 3,60	0,00	- 1,25
Q22_2	5,43±1,33	4,42±1,22	2,50	0,01	0,79

Degrees of freedom = 38. Group sizes = 20 (A) and 20 (B).

- 3) *ACT*: Grouping of questions Q1, Q7, and Q14 relating to “actionability” according to Witmer.
- 4) *SOUND*: Grouping of Q10 and Q11 questions relating to “sounds” according to Witmer.
- 5) *EXAM*: Grouping of questions Q13, Q17, and Q19 relating to the “possibility of examining the environment” according to Witmer.
- 6) *SELF*: Grouping of questions Q15 and Q16 relating to “self-assessment of self” according to Witmer.
- 7) *Q20, Q21, and Q22*: Specific questions related to the heuristics introduced
- 8) *S1 to S15*: Symptomatology of dizziness according to SSQ.

In addition, each of the variables in previous list was renamed with a “_1” suffix, if the data corresponds to the first test or with “_2,” regarding the second test. For example, SELF_1 corresponds to the grouping of Q15 and Q16 responses answered after the first test, while SELF_2 corresponds to the grouping of Q15 and Q16 responses answered after the second test.

1) *Statistical Analysis*: Table VII shows the numerical results of the Witmer questions and those added ad hoc for the experiment. For each value analyzed, the result of the first test and the second test are shown. This table includes the Student’s *t*-test to compare the means of both groups for all the values considered, as well as the *p*-value and the Cohen’s *d* as a measure of the effect size. These three evaluation values from the statistical analysis are also shown in the rest of the tables included in Section IV.

Regarding the *t*-student for independent samples, it can be seen that there are three data considered as relevant. On

TABLE VIII
T-TEST RESULTS FOR INDEPENDENT SAMPLES SSQ

Measure	Mean±SD (Group A)	Mean±SD (Group B)	t	p	d
S1_1	0,19±0,51	0,32±0,58	-0,72	0,24	-0,23
S1_2	0,38±0,86	0,42±1,02	-0,14	0,45	-0,04
S2_1	0,57±1,08	0,47±0,9	0,31	0,38	0,10
S2_2	0,57±1,03	0,42±0,77	0,52	0,30	0,17
S3_1	0,21±0,57	0,22±0,59	0,17	0,46	0,06
S3_2	0,24±0,54	0,21±0,54	0,16	0,44	0,05
S4_1	0,32±0,65	0,29±0,44	0,18	0,42	0,07
S4_2	0,62±1,36	0,21±0,71	1,17	0,12	0,39
S5_1	0,14±0,48	0±0	1,3	0,10	0,60
S5_2	0,33±0,86	0,05±0,23	1,38	0,09	0,52
S6_1	0,05±0,22	0,05±0,23	-0,07	0,47	-0,02
S6_2	0,00±0,00	0,05±0,23	-1,05	0,15	-0,46
S7_1	0,00±0,00	0,00±0,00	---	---	---
S7_2	0,00±0,00	0,00±0,00	---	---	---
S8_1	0,19±0,68	0,11±0,32	0,5	0,31	0,17
S8_2	0,29±0,9	0,21±0,42	0,33	0,37	0,11
S9_1	0,14±0,36	0,32±0,58	-1,14	0,13	-0,37
S9_2	0,14±0,48	0,32±0,58	-1,03	0,16	-0,33
S10_1	0,10±0,30	0,05±0,23	0,5	0,31	0,16
S10_2	0,10±0,30	0,00±0,00	1,38	0,09	0,63
S11_1	0,10±0,44	0,11±0,32	-0,08	0,47	-0,03
S11_2	0,10±0,44	0,21±0,42	-0,85	0,20	-0,27
S12_1	0,00±0,00	0,00±0,00	---	---	---
S12_2	0,10±0,30	0,00±0,00	1,38	0,09	0,63
S13_1	0,10±0,44	0,21±0,42	-0,85	0,20	-0,27
S13_2	0,05±0,22	0,11±0,32	-0,68	0,25	-0,22
S14_1	0,52±1,17	0,37±0,68	0,51	0,31	0,17
S14_2	0,57±1,25	0,47±1,12	0,26	0,40	0,08
S15_1	0,10±0,30	0,05±0,23	0,50	0,31	0,16
S15_2	0,10±0,30	0,05±0,23	0,50	0,31	0,16

Degrees of freedom = 38. Group sizes = 20 (A) and 20 (B).

the one hand, the responses to Q21_1-Q21_2 (I correctly perceived through the motion platform when a wheel went onto a piano on the road) and Q22_1-Q22_2 (These last two stimuli have helped to better perceive what was happening in the simulation) and on the other hand S3_2 (Stomach upset).

Regarding questions Q20 and Q21, a significant difference in users’ perception of pianos is observed when using heuristics. This significant difference is also supported by a large effect size, especially in Q21.

Analyzing the content of questions Q20_1/Q20_2 and Q21_1/Q21_2, the result observed in Q22_1/Q22_2 can be justified, where it is stated that users have perceived that the stimuli (shifting gears and pianos) have helped them to better integrate into the simulation that was taking place.

From the above, it can be concluded that there have been certain stimuli that users have perceived better with the heuristics applied than without.

Regarding the results of the SSQ, which are shown in Table VIII, there are no significant results to highlight.

2) *Paired Samples*: Regarding the results of the paired samples *t*-test, first, group A was analyzed, comparing the first test against the second, i.e., “WITHOUT heuristics” against “WITH heuristics.” Second, group B was analyzed, comparing the first test against the second, i.e., “WITH heuristics” against “WITHOUT heuristics.”

TABLE IX
T-TEST RESULTS FOR PAIRED SAMPLES (GROUP A)

First Without H, then With H					
Measure	Mean±SD (Without H)	Mean±SD (With H)	t	p	d
REAL	4,91±0,61	5,17±0,67	-2,46	0,01	-0,39
INT	4,76±0,62	5,24±0,62	-2,91	0,00	-0,76
ACT	5,11±0,5	5,16±0,66	-0,43	0,34	-0,08
SOUND	5,07±0,78	4,98±0,9	0,53	0,30	0,11
EXAM	4,84±0,9	5,11±0,74	-1,97	0,32	-0,33
SELF	5,31±0,68	5,38±0,67	-0,65	0,26	-0,11
Q20	4,48±1,97	4,9±1,51	-1,53	0,07	-0,25
Q21	3,62±1,86	5,48±1,12	-4,81	0,00	-1,25
Q22	3,95±1,83	5,43±1,33	-3,93	0,00	-0,94
Degrees of freedom = 19					

TABLE X
T-TEST RESULTS FOR PAIRED SAMPLES (GROUP B)

First With H, then Without H					
Measure	Mean±SD (With H)	Mean±SD (Without H)	t	p	d
REAL	4,89±0,74	4,85±0,69	0,32	0,38	0,05
INT	4,84±0,90	4,84±1,01	0,00	0,50	0,00
ACT	5,05±0,81	5,16±0,76	-1,10	0,14	-0,13
SOUND	4,92±1,02	5,08±1,15	-1,84	0,41	-0,15
EXAM	5,00±0,90	4,97±0,79	0,26	0,40	0,04
SELF	5,26±0,93	5,34±0,78	-0,62	0,27	-0,09
Q20	4,95±1,27	4,47±1,02	1,25	0,11	0,41
Q21	5,63±0,76	3,84±1,71	4,10	0,00	1,45
Q22	5,58±0,77	4,42±1,22	3,54	0,00	1,17
Degrees of freedom = 19					

Looking at the tables and more specifically at the Witmer values for group A (Table IX), it can be seen that users perceive greater realism and better interaction with the simulator in the tests in which the heuristics were included compared to those in which they were not.

The fact that this only is significant in group A and not in group B shows that the order is important. Considering that most of the users had never tried a motion-based simulator before, it is normal that they answered the first questionnaire with relatively high values (surprise effect). In group A (first test without heuristics), the values of the second questionnaire improved significantly, while in group B (first test with heuristics), although they also improved, the improvement on the second test was not so high.

In addition, the answers given in Q21 and Q22 are striking, with a $p < 10^{-3}$ and a noticeable effect size (Cohen's $d > 0.8$ for both cases), in which it is observed that the perception of the piano and the gear changes were much better with the heuristics than without them. Regarding these two questions, it can be seen that Tables IX and X agree with Table VI (better sense of the piano and better sense of both highlighted stimuli). The coincidence in results of independent samples and paired samples studies reinforces the validity of the study and the reliability of the data collected.

3) ANOVA Analysis: A total of 11 ANOVA analyses were carried out on the following variables.

- 1) *Dependent Variables:* REAL, INT, ACT, SOUND, EXAM, SELF, Q20, Q21, Q22, sum of SSQ variables after the first test, sum of SSQ variables after the second test. Only the SSQ values have been added because these are data (symptoms) that can be managed jointly, that is, the dizziness can be measured as a variable between 0 and 80 (six points * 15 symptoms) points, where 0 would imply that there is no dizziness and 80 that they have felt all the symptoms to the maximum.
- 2) *Independent Variables for Each Dependent Value:*
 - a) Variable that includes the first test in Group A (without heuristics) and the first test in Group B (with heuristics) (denoted as 'FirstTest').
 - b) Gender (denoted as 'M_F').
 - c) Age.
 - d) Driving License – yes, no (denoted as 'License').
 - e) Year of obtaining the driver's license (YearLic).
 - f) FirstTest* M_F.
 - g) FirstTest*Age.
 - h) FirstTest* License.
 - i) FirstTest*YearLic.
 - j) M_F *Age.
 - k) M_F * License.
 - l) M_F *YearLic.
 - m) Age* License.
 - n) Age*YearLic.
 - o) License*YearLic.

Among all the combinations of factors evaluated, the difference between men and women is striking, where the significance is very relevant in the possibility of examining the environment (EXAM) and in the user's self-assessment (SELF) during the simulator test. Concretely, results showed significant differences for the EXAM variable between the gender groups ($F[1, 7.54] = 5.007$, $p = 0.045$, $\eta^2 = 0.294$) and the YearLic group ($F[7, 4.25] = 4.513$, $p = 0.011$, $\eta^2 = 0.725$). Additionally, a noticeable difference was obtained for the SELF variable ($F[3, 2.99] = 8.231$, $p = 0.003$, $\eta^2 = 0.673$), when the participants were divided into three groups according to their age. The study results indicate that there were significant differences in performance between the two study groups. It was also observed that there was a higher incidence of dizziness reported by the female participants in both groups. These results confirm the findings of Hancock [3].

Regarding the dependent variable Q22, it is worth highlighting the people who have received training courses and who had previously tested driving simulators with a motion platform. The users of this group emphasize that they perceived the stimuli of the pianos and gear changes much better with the heuristics than without them ($F[1, 3.12] = 5.739$, $p = 0.022$, $\eta^2 = 0.144$). It should be noted that this data is of particular relevance to the researchers, as this group is assumed to be the most expert in both simulation and driving.

Regarding the questions related to motion sickness, it was observed that women reported higher levels of motion sickness compared to men. Additionally, it was found that younger participants reported lower levels of motion sickness, which may be related to their familiarity with technology.

TABLE XI
WITMER FACTOR CORRELATION TABLE FOR TESTS
“WITHOUT HEURISTICS”

		WITHOUT HEURISTICS					
		REAL	INT	ACT	SOUND	EXAM	SELF
REAL	<i>p</i>	0,000	0,769	0,479	0,441	0,404	0,188
	<i>Sig.</i>	0,000	0,001	0,028	0,046	0,069	0,415
INT	<i>p</i>	0,769	0,000	0,571	0,293	0,195	0,064
	<i>Sig.</i>	0,001	0,000	0,007	0,197	0,397	0,781
ACT	<i>p</i>	0,479	0,571	0,000	0,344	0,386	0,336
	<i>Sig.</i>	0,028	0,007	0,000	0,127	0,084	0,136
SOUND	<i>p</i>	0,441	0,293	0,344	0,000	0,100	0,121
	<i>Sig.</i>	0,046	0,197	0,127	0,000	0,067	0,600
EXAM	<i>p</i>	0,404	0,195	0,386	0,100	0,000	0,409
	<i>Sig.</i>	0,069	0,397	0,084	0,668	0,000	0,065
SELF	<i>p</i>	0,188	0,064	0,336	0,121	0,409	0,000
	<i>Sig.</i>	0,415	0,781	0,136	0,600	0,065	0,000

TABLE XII
WITMER FACTOR CORRELATION TABLE FOR TESTS “WITH HEURISTICS”

		WITH HEURISTICS					
		REAL	INT	ACT	SOUND	EXAM	SELF
REAL	<i>p</i>	0,000	0,046	0,635	0,457	0,636	0,719
	<i>Sig.</i>	0,000	0,047	0,003	0,049	0,003	0,001
INT	<i>p</i>	0,461	0,000	0,597	0,441	0,320	0,119
	<i>Sig.</i>	0,047	0,000	0,007	0,058	0,182	0,629
ACT	<i>p</i>	0,635	0,597	0,000	0,780	0,717	0,666
	<i>Sig.</i>	0,003	0,007	0,000	0,001	0,001	0,002
SOUND	<i>p</i>	0,457	0,441	0,780	0,000	0,776	0,652
	<i>Sig.</i>	0,049	0,058	0,001	0,000	0,001	0,002
EXAM	<i>p</i>	0,636	0,320	0,717	0,776	0,000	0,725
	<i>Sig.</i>	0,003	0,182	0,001	0,001	0,000	0,001
SELF	<i>p</i>	0,719	0,119	0,666	0,652	0,725	0,000
	<i>Sig.</i>	0,001	0,629	0,002	0,002	0,001	0,000

Finally, as collateral result, it can be observed that two other relevant factors are the years since obtaining the driving license and the age of the drivers. These factors are directly related and it has been observed, according to demographic data, that the age at which users obtain their driving license is 19 years old. Therefore, we will treat both factors as one in order to state, based on the results, that the younger the user, the higher their self-assessment of their performance (SELF) in the simulation and their ability to examine the recreated environment (EXAM). This result is not surprising, as users’ daily relationship with new technologies and their familiarity with them is directly related to their age. The younger they are, the more influence digital screens, video game consoles, etc., have had on their daily lives and, therefore, the better they perform in a computer graphics-based simulator.

4) *Statistical Correlation:* In this section we will study the correlations between the different variables that have been analyzed. For each one of these, the Pearson CC and significance are evaluated. Values with a Pearson value <-0.7 or >0.7 and significance <0.05 will be considered as correlating. Tables XI and XII show the results.

The first table shows a clear correlation between realism and interface quality. Specifically, and based on the questions grouped in the “INT” factor according to Witmer, the authors

TABLE XIII
COUNTERBALANCED PAIRED SAMPLE MEANS OF
ALL PARTICIPANTS IN THE STUDY

	Average WITHOUT Heuristics (0-6)	Average WITH Heuristics (0-6)	Difference (0-6)
Q1	5,550	5,600	0,050
Q2	4,800	5,050	0,250
Q3	4,875	4,925	0,050
Q4	5,000	5,200	0,200
Q5	4,875	4,975	0,100
Q6	4,475	4,650	0,175
Q7	4,925	4,750	-0,175
Q8	4,900	5,025	0,125
Q9	---	---	---
Q10	5,275	5,175	-0,100
Q11	4,875	4,725	-0,150
Q12	---	---	---
Q13	4,425	4,550	0,125
Q14	4,925	4,975	0,050
Q15	5,300	5,300	0,000
Q16	5,350	5,350	0,000
Q17	5,050	5,250	0,200
Q18	5,175	5,425	0,250
Q19	5,225	5,375	0,150
Q20	4,500	4,925	0,425
Q21	3,725	5,550	1,825
Q22	4,175	5,500	1,325

understand INT as questions related to the graphic environment and visual quality. This correlation seems obvious, since the better the visual quality, the greater the realism. The surprising part of this correlation is that it does not show up in the second of the tables, which measures the values with the heuristics applied.

Similarly, several correlations appear in the second table that are not apparent in the first. This singularity could be interpreted as being due to the strong crossover between the various questions that are part of Witmer’s groupings. For example, Q7 - “My vision actively explored the entire environment as I used the simulator,” belonging to the ACT group and Q13 - “I was able to examine the elements of the simulation from multiple points of view,” belonging to the EXAM group, for the author these are questions that are closely linked, as both are related to the visual system of the simulator (FOV and graphic quality) and therefore, their correlation seems evident.

The fact that there are many more variables with a high correlation in the second table, shows that users have answered more consistently when heuristics are present than when they are not.

5) *Counter-Balanced Paired Samples:* Another analysis carried out was to observe the difference in the means of the results with and without heuristics applied to the responses of all the participants in the study. A *t*-test was applied, finding significant results in Q20, Q21, and Q22, with $p = 0.049$, $p < 10^{-6}$ and $p < 10^{-5}$, respectively. These are the questions that directly inferred the events to which the heuristics were applied. Table XIII shows these mean results and their difference.

Fig. 7. Record of vestibular sensations recorded by users in real time during the experiment.

The values for the Witmer questionnaire did not show significant results. Neither did the SSQ values, where it is confirmed that the version with heuristics does not interfere with whether people become more or less dizzy during the use of the simulator.

As will be seen below, the data recorded in real time agree with the mean difference results shown in the table above.

From this, it can be concluded that users have perfectly perceived the two events they were intended to perceive, i.e., gear changes and wheel departures from the carriageway, so the objective of the application of heuristics seems to have been met.

B. Numerical Analysis of Real-Time Recorded Data

For each user in the experiment, two .dat files were generated with the information recorded in real time by the user regarding the sensation (good or bad) that the motion platform was transmitting.

As mentioned above, of the 42 users who performed the tests, only 40 of them were considered valid users, as two of them could not stay on the simulator for more than 10 s due to the feeling of dizziness.

The data recorded shows that users did not touch the joystick except at specific times during the simulation. That is, most of the time the value transmitted was 0 (or very near to 0), whereas when users detected something that caught their attention, good or bad, they moved the joystick and the value recorded was proportional to the good or bad feeling they had.

The data obtained were measured, first “without heuristics” and then “with heuristics.” Then, “with”-’without” were subtracted, and finally passed through a Wiener adaptive filter, with the aim of eliminating noise, to obtain the graph shown in Fig. 7.

After observing the results, which clearly show five peaks that differ from 0, we labeled, thanks to the time stamps, what happened at those five instants of the simulation.

In Fig. 7 it can be observed that the five peaks correspond to two different events. The first one is related to the rapid reduction in speed when approaching curves. This event is directly related to the very fast gear changes in a short time (i.e., change from third to first in few seconds). The second one, that also is most striking one, is related to the piano.

The last of the peaks corresponds to the end of the circuit, which finished with a series of zigzagging curves, a significant reduction in speed and subsequent acceleration once the curve has been passed. In conversations with users, these reported that at that exact moment they felt more like they were on a boat or a plane than in a car.

From the rest of the peaks observed on the graph, it is clear that both effects introduced by heuristics, both the gear changes and the piano, have had a very satisfactory effect on the vestibular perception of the users.

C. System Stability

The proposed heuristic-enhanced CWA was carefully designed to preserve the overall stability and safety of the motion cueing system. While a formal Lyapunov-based analysis of global system stability—including the human-in-the-loop and the platform’s servo controllers— is beyond the scope of this study, we provide both theoretical and empirical justifications supporting the stability of the proposed approach.

1) *Theoretical Considerations:* The classical CWA is composed of linear filters (high-pass and low-pass) and integrators that ensure bounded-output behavior in response to bounded inputs. This structure guarantees that, for any finite acceleration or angular velocity input, the platform motion remains within safe operational limits. Our proposed heuristic enhancement modifies the system output by injecting short-duration, bounded signals $h(t)$ only when predefined trigger events are detected. The enhanced output can be written as (3). Since all heuristic signals are explicitly limited in amplitude and duration, and are added at the output stage without modifying the internal feedback or filtering structure, the system remains bounded-input bounded-output (BIBO) stable. The core washout algorithm continues to govern the platform’s return to equilibrium, ensuring that residual platform motion is smoothly cancelled over time.

2) *Empirical Validation:* During all experimental trials ($N = 40$ participants), the 6-DoF motion platform remained well within its mechanical limits in all degrees of freedom. For example, the largest pitch angles generated during heuristic-triggered gear shift events remained below $\pm 5^\circ$, far from the platform’s $\pm 20^\circ$ physical limit. Similarly, vertical displacements associated with simulated bumps or road irregularities stayed within ± 30 mm, while the platform’s maximum heave range is ± 150 mm. In all cases, the safety envelope was preserved with a wide operational margin.

Furthermore, motion behavior remained smooth and continuous, with no overshoots, oscillations, or actuator saturations observed following any heuristic injection. The platform’s servomotors responded accurately to the combined CWA and heuristic commands, and the washout filters continued to recenter the platform after each transient motion.

3) *Subjective Observations:* No participants reported motion anomalies, discomfort, or instability related to the heuristic cues. On the contrary, user feedback indicated improved motion realism during events such as gear changes or minor impacts, without noticeable degradation of comfort or synchronization. The absence of negative subjective reports

reinforces the empirical evidence that the heuristic-enhanced algorithm maintains stable and natural platform behavior under realistic driving conditions.

D. Simulator Sickness and User Comfort

To evaluate the comfort and safety of the simulation, participants completed the SSQ after each trial. The SSQ results indicate that the heuristic-enhanced CWA does not introduce any additional simulator sickness compared to the standard CWA. Across our pool of 40 participants, there were no significant differences in SSQ symptom scores between the “with heuristics” and “without heuristics” conditions (all p -values > 0.05 when comparing conditions for each symptom category). Importantly, no participant reported experiencing nausea, disorientation, or strong discomfort in either condition. This suggests that the added motion cues did not negatively affect users’ physical comfort or well-being. We also examined the data across different demographic groups to ensure the result is robust. The absence of increased sickness symptoms held true for participants of varying ages and genders, as well as for those with and without prior simulator experience. In other words, the introduction of heuristic motion cues did not adversely affect any specific subgroup of users. These findings imply that our approach enhances motion cue perception without creating the sensory mismatches that can lead to motion sickness. We attribute the lack of simulator sickness to the design of the heuristic cues: by reinforcing critical motion signals in synchrony with the visual simulation, the system maintains sensory consistency. Therefore, users benefit from improved motion realism without experiencing the dizziness or discomfort that can occur when vestibular and visual cues are misaligned. This result is significant because it demonstrates that increasing motion fidelity through heuristics can be achieved without compromising user comfort, even for a diverse user audience. We have thus shown that our heuristic-enhanced algorithm can improve the driving simulator experience (in terms of cue authenticity and presence) while keeping simulator-induced sickness at a minimal level.

E. Scope of Comparison With Other MCA Approaches

In this study, the CWA was chosen as the baseline MCA because it is one of the most widely used motion cueing strategies in professional driving simulators. We focused on improving this classical algorithm due to its prevalence and well-understood behavior. Although many advanced MCAs (e.g., adaptive algorithms, optimal control schemes, or MPC-based approaches) have been proposed in the literature, performing a rigorous quantitative comparison against each of these under identical conditions was beyond the scope of our work. Implementing and fine tuning each alternative algorithm for a fair head-to-head evaluation using optimal conditions for all of them is impractical [10]. In fact, there is currently no consensus on a single “best” MCA for all scenarios, and each approach often requires careful parameter adjustment and proprietary know-how. Therefore, rather than claim superiority over all MCA types, our goal is to demonstrate that the introduction of targeted heuristics can enhance an established

baseline algorithm’s performance. The results show that even a standard CWA can be significantly improved in motion cue fidelity by the proposed heuristic modifications. It is also important to emphasize that the proposed heuristic framework is general and could be applied to other MCA paradigms as well; however, evaluating it across different algorithms (each with unique tuning and implementation considerations) is left for future work.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The present study expands upon previous research conducted by the authors, who observed that the MCAs realistically reproduce the motion that users expect to receive through motion platforms, but certain signals are eliminated. These lost signals, which would eventually become vestibular sensations that the user would receive, may well contain very useful information as to what is happening at a certain moment in a simulation. If this information is lost and the timing of the loss is relevant to the purpose of the simulator, e.g., for driving training simulators, the user will not be receiving adequate stimuli and will therefore act accordingly.

To try to solve this problem, the authors hypothesize that certain heuristic signals should be introduced into the MCAs to parallel the internal calculations of the MCA and to ensure that they are adequately transmitted to the user without affecting the level of presence.

In order to test this hypothesis, a highly immersive driving simulator, consisting of a 6DOF motion platform with projection screen (FOVH 300°) and on-board driving cockpit, has been used and tested by 40 users. Each participant tested one version of the classical washout MCA with applied heuristics and one version without applied heuristics.

From these analyses it is concluded that users perceive the events marked as important with the version with heuristics in a more satisfactory way. Also, the modified MCA with heuristics does not affect the level of presence in the simulator.

Furthermore, it is concluded that these events have helped users to better perceive what was happening at each instant in the simulation.

Therefore, based on the results of the study, it can be stated that the use of heuristics for specific events that are usually filtered by MCA is a good alternative when the developer of a simulator wants to make sure that the vestibular sensations of those events are not lost.

It should be noted that, if these events are important for the use of the simulator, as is the example case on which this experiment is based and which consists of driving training simulators, by using the type of heuristics implemented in this experiment, the vestibular perception of these events significantly increases.

The key to making satisfactory use of the heuristic system described in this article lies in being able to predict in advance the specific events that are lost due to the use of MCA. Therefore, a study should be carried out to objectively parameterize those stimuli that are important for certain types of training simulators (airplane, helicopter, ship, etc.).

With the data from this new study, it will be possible to reproduce the experiment shown in this article to validate the use of heuristics on other simulators to improve user perception in VR-based simulators.

Moreover, since the CWA is the most commonly used, but not the only one, it would be convenient to perform this same experiment but applied to different types of MCA, such as adaptive, optimal or predictive.

Finally, this experiment has tested a specific heuristic approach, but there are many other alternatives that could be used to ensure that certain previously selected stimuli are transmitted realistically to users. The necessary implementations should be carried out to test new heuristic methods and evaluate them properly.

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